

3 repeated

NMTC---BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION—DECEMBER, 2015
(RGN 14 PUBLIC HEALTH NURSING
TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS

- Answer all questions
- Answer each question in a separate answer booklet
- All questions carry equal marks (20 marks Each)
- Carefully read questions and provide only relevant answers, no mark for irrelevant answers
- Answers provided beyond the number specified attract no mark

Question One

Mr. Afedzi Mensah, aged 35 years was admitted to your ward with pulmonary tuberculosis.

- a) Enumerate any **five (5)** predisposing causes of pulmonary tuberculosis - 5marks
- b) Mention **five (5)** cardinal signs of pulmonary tuberculosis - 5marks
- c) Tuberculosis continues to be a disease of public health concern in Ghana. State any three reasons why this is so. - 3marks.
- d) What method can be put in place to prevent the spread of tuberculosis at the community level? - 7 marks

Question Two

A mother reported at the clinic with her 10 months old infant who had passed five stools in the night.

- a. Explain the possible causes of the condition in respect of the following:
 - i. Environment (2 causes) - 4marks
 - ii. Preparation of infants food (3 causes) - 6marks
- b. Describe **five (5)** ways of preventing diarrhoea in infants - 5marks
- c. List **five (5)** child survival strategies - 5marks

Question Three

Health statistics play a vital role in the health delivery system.

- a) List **five (5)** importance of health statics - 5marks
- b) Enumerate **five (5)** causes of home accidents - 5marks
- c) Describe general preventive measures of home accidents in the under fives. - 10marks

2

5

NMTC - BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION-MAY, 2015
D15 /RM10 HRGN/HMEW PUBLIC HEALTH
TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks

Question One

- a. Define Immunization - 5 marks
- b. List and explain the main techniques of home visit - 8 marks
- c. Give seven (7) possible reasons for nursing mothers to default in immunization - 7 marks

Question Two

- a. Define and show by a diagram the Cold chain System - 7 marks
- b. Home Visit is the core of preventing nursing. The nurse in the home gives the opportunity to determine in what areas of the teaching he / she can be of help. Explain six (6) points under planning and preparation for Home Visit in general - 6 marks
- c. Immunization aims at the coverage of 80% of children 0 – 5 years to be protected from vaccine preventable diseases. What are the roles of the (7) stakeholders in immunization in accordance with the policy in Ghana? - 7 marks

Question Three

You have been invited to give a talk on “Teenage pregnancy” to the people of Nyankonse, a farming community in the Brong Ahafo region.

- a. Outline SEVEN (7) causes of teenage pregnancy (7marks)
- b. State EIGHT (8) effects of teenage pregnancy. (4marks)
- c. Enumerate NINE (9) points how teenage pregnancy can be reduced. (9marks)

Question Four

- a. Describe the principles of the Primary Health Care (10marks)
- b. State any FIVE (5) components of Primary Health Care (5marks)
- c. Describe FIVE (5) duties of the community health nurse (5marks)

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC -BEREKUM /ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – DECEMBER, 2018
RGN 19/RM 14 PUBLIC HEALTH NURSING
TIME ALLOWED: 2 HRS.
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

- a. What is Occupational Health? - 2 marks
- b. Give the three (3) reasons for occupational health. - 3 marks
- c. List ten (10) benefit of occupational health. - 5 marks
- d. Mention the types/ forms of occupational hazards and give two examples each. - 10 marks

Question Two

- a. What does the abbreviation CHPS stand for? - 1 mark
- b. What are the three (3) objectives of CHPS policy? - 3 marks
- c. State five (5) CHPS process. - 5 marks
- d. Give five(5) members who are front line actors of CHPS. - 5 marks
- e. List the six (6) milestone of the CHPS process - 6 marks

Question Three

- a. Currently Ghana has targeted 23 diseases for surveillance. Outline three (3) criteria used in selecting these diseases. - 3marks
- b. Identify four (4) diseases that are classified as “epidemic prone diseases” - 4marks
- c. What are the three (3) main elements that must occur to form a carrier state - 3marks
- d. Draw the disease transmission circle - 6marks
- e. Protecting the disease susceptible host is one of the methods in communicable diseases. What four (4) Strategies will you employ to protect the susceptible host - 4marks

Question Four

A 10 weeks old baby Nyameama was brought to the child welfare clinic for her growth monitoring and immunizations.

- a. Under the Expanded Programme on immunization determine in a tabular form the vaccines that baby Nyameama will receive, their respective dosages and the desired route/site of administration of each of the vaccines. - 12marks
- b. Mention any (4) immunization delivery strategies - 2marks
- c. The four (4) main characteristics of the immune system - 2marks
- d. Mention any Four (4) staff/provider characteristics of adolescent friendly health service -4marks

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC-BEREKUM/ST. MARY'S CAMPUS- DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION MAY 2018
RGN 18 & RM 13 PHN 321 PUBLIC HEALTH NURSING
TIME ALLOWED; 2 HRS
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

- *Answer all questions.*
- *Each question must be answered in a separate booklet*
- *Each question carries 20marks*
- *Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers*
- *Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.*

Question One

- a. Outline the Child Survival Strategies as indicated in the Selective Primary Health Care - 7marks
- b. State the **FIVE (5)** Principles of Primary Health Care - 5marks
- c. What **FIVE (5)** criteria will you consider in selecting a community to be used as CHPS zone? - 5 marks
- d. Identify the **SIX (6)** milestones of the CHPS process - 3marks

Question Two

Madam Ndo Kaya has a six weeks baby Kojo, who is due for Child Welfare Clinic (CWC).

- a. State FOUR (4) objectives of Child Welfare Clinic (CWC). - 2marks
- b. List Six (6) activities that are carried out at the Child Welfare Clinic. - 3marks
- c. Identify any Six (6) factors that can negatively affect the patronage of Child Welfare Clinic in your community - 3marks
- d. In a tabular form; indicate the vaccines that baby Kojo will receive at the clinic, the dosage of each vaccine and route/ site of administration - 12marks

Question Three

- a. Currently Ghana has targeted 23 diseases for surveillance. Outline FIVE (5) criteria used in selecting these diseases. - 5marks
- b. Identify four (4) diseases that are classified as "epidemic prone diseases" - 4marks
- c. Identify the three (3) main elements that must occur to form a carrier state - 6marks
- d. Outline FIVE (5) environmental factors that can affect disease transmission - 5marks

Question Four

- a. Mention and explain the levels of disease prevention. - 6 marks
- b. Enumerate six (6) basic requirements for sound PHC (Primary Health Care). - 6 marks
- c. Mention four (4) uses of surveillance data. - 4 marks
- d. Mention four (4) characteristics of surveillance. - 4 marks

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC-BEREKUM/ ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION-MAY 2017
RGN 17 & RM 12 PHN 321 PUBLIC HEALTH NURSING
TIME ALLOWED: 2HRS
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

QUESTION ONE

Madam Yaa Tawia has a six weeks baby Kojo, who is due for Child Welfare Clinic (CWC).

- a. State five (5) objectives of Child Welfare Clinic (CWC). - 5 marks
- b. List six (6) activities that are carried out at the Child Welfare Clinic. - 6 marks
- c. Report from the sub-district indicates low attendance at CWC. Identify any **six (6)** possible causes of the decline
6marks -
- d. Describe six (6) benefits of child welfare clinic - 3marks

Question Two

- a. State the components of occupational hazards - 5marks
- b. Mention (6) benefit of occupational health. - 6 marks
- c. Identify eight (8) members of occupational health team - 4marks
- d. State five (5) examples of physical hazards at the work place - 5marks

Question Three

- a. Draw the disease transmission cycle - 6marks
- b. Mention the **three (3)** main elements that must occur to form a carrier state - 4marks
- c. Mention **four (4)** diseases that can be transmitted through sexual intercourse. - 4 marks
- d. Briefly explain unsafe abortion to a first year nursing student - 4marks
- e. Give **two (2)** complications of unsafe abortion - 2marks

Question Four

- a. Outline the contents of the selective primary health care - 7marks
- b. State the **FIVE (5)** Principles of Primary Health Care - 5marks
- c. What five (5) criteria will you consider in selecting a community to be used as CHPS zone?
- 5marks
- d. The CHPS process has **six (6)** milestones. What are they? - 3marks

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION-MAY, 2016
D16 /RM11 HRGN/HMEW PUBLIC HEALTH
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ MINUTES

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks

Question one

- | | |
|---|--------|
| a. Describe how you will prepare for a school hygiene inspection | 6marks |
| Define carrier in disease transmission | 2marks |
| c. State the three elements that have to occur to form a carrier state | 6marks |
| d. Mention six (6) members of the school health team | 6marks |

Question Two

- | | |
|--|--------|
| a. State the FIVE (5) Principles of Primary Health Care | 5marks |
| b. Outline the contents of the selective primary health care | 7marks |
| c. What are the six (6) milestones in the CHPS process | 6marks |
| d. List four (4) functions of the occupational health nurse | 2marks |

Question Three

- | | |
|--|--------|
| a. Immunization stimulates and activates our body's immunologic defense in the preparation of meeting the challenge of future exposure to diseases. Give four (4) points considered in immunization on the recommended schedule. | 4marks |
| b. State any three (3) aims of Home Visit | 3marks |
| c. Define Vaccine and give the three types of vaccines. | 3marks |
| d. State three (3) Essential Elements of Cold Chain that helps to manage Cold Chain System Effective | 3marks |
| e. Enumerate six (6) points to remember in managing Vaccine potency. | 3marks |
| f. State four (4) tasks that need to be performed before any Immunization session is carried out. | 4marks |

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC - BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – APRIL 2021
POST NAC NAP PUBLIC HEALTH AND FAMILY PLANNING
TIME ALLOWED: 1HR.
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will attract any mark.

QUESTION ONE

Madam Ananse, a 32 year old and para three (3) came to your facility for a family planning method. Madam Ananse stressed that she wish to give birth again and you used the GATHER counseling method to counsel her.

- a. What is the full meaning of the acronym GATHER? - 6 marks
- b. How will you conduct the first stage (G) of the GATHER counseling method? - 8 marks
- c. Mention any SIX (6) Natural family methods - 6 marks

QUESTION TWO

- a. You were part of the committee in setting up a CHPS center. What criteria FIVE (5) would you consider when setting up the zone? - 5 marks
- b. What steps would you go through in implementing the CHPS - 10 marks
- c. Florence an adolescent is refusing to seek Reproductive Health services. What could be the reason? - 5 marks

QUESTION THREE

- a. Fati is 18 years old which shows she is a late adolescent. Mention SIX (6) developmental changes that will occur. - 6 marks
- b. For a Surveillance to be well-conducted, what EIGHT (8) surveillance characteristics Should it Posses. - 8 marks
- c. As a midwife going for home visiting, explain the Phases and activities of home visiting up to the second phase - 6 marks

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- APRIL 2021
RM 16 (PHN 321) PUBLIC HEALTH NURSING
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HR.
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will attract any mark.

QUESTION ONE

Integrated management of childhood and neonatal illness is a strategy to reduce morbidity and mortality in under five children in relation to the major killers.

- a. What are the diseases classified under the IMCNI as “major killers”? - 2½marks
- b. The implementation of the IMCNI strategy involves three major components. What are these components?
- 1½marks
- c. The case management of a sick child brought to a first-level health facility under the IMCNI strategy includes a number of important elements. Mention any FOUR (4) of these elements - 4marks
- d. Why will you recommend IMCNI strategy in managing childhood illness in your locality where the incidence of infant morbidity and mortality rate is high? (Give five reasons) - 5 marks

School Health Services is one of the components of the reproductive and child health.

- e. As a school nurse how will you prepare for school hygiene inspection? - 5marks
- f. Which FOUR (4) areas will you inspect during school environmental hygiene inspection? - 2marks

QUESTION TWO

- a. Madam Kaya has been described as “a carrier” of a disease in the community. What three (3) characteristics must she possess? - 3marks
- b. Identify four (4) diseases that are classified as “epidemic prone diseases” - 2marks
- c. What Four (4) criteria will you use to select diseases as targets for surveillance? - 4marks

Madam NT has been referred from Nantey Health Centre to Nyanya District Hospital as a result of Post-Partum Haemorrhage after delivery.

- d. What THREE (3) reasons may be assigned for referring Madam NT? - 3marks
- e. What procedure will you follow in referring the client? - 5marks
- f. State any SIX (6) factors you will consider before referring the patient? - 3marks

Pease Turn Over

QUESTION THREE

- a. The Public Health Unit of Ghana Health Service is encouraging majority of Ghanaians to receive the AstraZeneca vaccine against Covid-19 so as to achieve herd immunity. What **SIX (6)** barriers can affect the ministry's effort in achieving herd immunity? - 6marks?
- b. State the **TWO (2)** absolute contraindications of immunization under the EPI - 2marks
- c. Ghana has policies regarding immunization and vitamin supplementation. Mention three of these policies - 3marks

Madam Nko brought her 10 weeks old baby to the child welfare clinic for routine immunization.

- d. In a tabular form, indicate all the vaccines that the child will receive, the dosage of each vaccine and the site/route of administration of each of the vaccines - 6marks
- e. What **THREE (3)** responsibilities of the nurse will motivate Madam Nko to continue immunizing her child? - 3marks?

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- APRIL 2021
PUBLIC HEALTH NURSING
TIME ALLOWED: 60 MINUTES
OBJECTIVE TEST RM 16

INSTRUCTIONS

For each of the following questions, CIRCLE the most appropriate answer.

- 1. Primary health care is a total approach to community development. Which of the following is an indicator of success in the use of the primary health care approach?
 - A. Health programs are sustained according to the level of development of the community
 - B. Health services are provided free of charge to individuals and families
 - C. Health workers are able to provide care based on identified health needs of the people
 - D. Local officials are empowered as the major decision makers in matters of health

- 2. Which of the following women should the midwife consider as special targets for family planning? Those
 - A. who have two children or more
 - B. with medical conditions such as anaemia
 - C. younger than 20 years and older than 35 years
 - D. who just had a delivery within the past 6 weeks

INDEX NUMBER.....

HFNMTC-BEREKUM

END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – APRIL 2021

(RGN 21) PHN 321 PUBLIC HEALTH NURSING

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HR.

INSTRUCTIONS

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

QUESTION ONE

- a. The Public Health Unit of Ghana Health Service is encouraging majority of Ghanaians to receive the AstraZeneca vaccine against Covid-19 so as to achieve herd immunity. What SIX (6) barriers can affect the ministry's effort in achieving herd immunity? - 6marks
- b. State the TWO (2) absolute contraindications of immunization under the EPI - 2marks
- c. Ghana has policies regarding immunization and vitamin supplementation. Mention three of these policies - 3marks

Madam Nko brought her 10 weeks old baby to the child welfare clinic for routine immunization.

- d. In a tabular form, indicate all the vaccines that the child will receive, the dosage of each vaccine and the site/route of administration of each of the vaccines - 6marks
- e. What THREE (3) responsibilities of the nurse will motivate Madam Nko to continue immunizing her child? - 3marks

QUESTION TWO

- a. The Primary Health Care Concept was grounded on five principles. State these principles - 5marks
- b. As a member of the District Health Management Team what Five (5) criteria will you consider when selecting a community to be used as a CHPS zone? - 5marks
- c. State the SIX milestones of the Community Based Health Planning and Services - 3marks
- d. Enumerate any Seven (7) functions of Level B (Health Centre) - 7marks

Please Turn Over

QUESTION THREE

- a. Integrated management of childhood and neonatal illness is a strategy to reduce morbidity and mortality in under five children in relation to the major killers.
- i. What are the diseases classified under the IMCNI as “major killers”? - 2½marks
 - ii. The implementation of the IMCNI strategy involves three major components. What are these components? - 1½marks
 - iii. The case management of a sick child brought to a first-level health facility under the IMCNI strategy includes a number of important elements. Mention any FOUR (4) of these elements - 4marks
 - iv. Why will you recommend IMCNI strategy in managing childhood illness in your locality where the incidence of infant morbidity and mortality rate is high? (Give five reasons) - 5marks
- b. i. Madam Kaya has been described as “a carrier” of a disease in the community. What three (3) characteristics must she possess? - 3marks
- ii. What Four (4) criteria will you use to select diseases as targets for surveillance? - 4marks

HFNMTC – BEREKUM - CAMPUS
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION, DECEMBER, 2018
POST NAC/NAP I PUBLIC HEALTH NURSING
TIME ALLOWED: 45 MINUTES

OBJECTIVES Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

- a. Currently Ghana has targeted 23 diseases for surveillance. Outline three (3) criteria used in selecting these diseases. - 3marks
- b. Identify four (4) diseases that are classified as “epidemic prone diseases” - 2marks
- c. What are the **three (3)** main elements that must occur to form a carrier state - 6marks
- d. Draw the disease transmission circle - 6marks
- e. Protecting the susceptible host is one of the methods in controlling communicable diseases. What **three (3)** strategies will you employ to protect the susceptible host? - 3marks

Question Two

A 10 weeks old baby Nyameama was brought to the child welfare clinic for her growth monitoring and immunizations.

- a. Under the Expanded Programme on immunization determine in a tabular form the vaccines that baby Nyameama will receive, their respective dosages and the desired route/site of administration of each of the vaccines - 12marks
- b. Identify any four (4) immunization strategies - 2marks
- c. Mention the four (4) main characteristics of the immune system - 2marks
- d. Adolescent health services are very important in meeting their reproductive health needs. Mention any four (4) provider characteristics of adolescent friendly health service - 4marks

Question Three

Madam Ananse, a 32 year old and para-three(3) came to your facility for a family planning method. Madam Ananse stressed that she wish to give birth again and you used the GATHER counseling method to counsel her.

- a. Explain the acronym GATHER? - 4 marks
- b. Vividly explain the third step of the above counseling method. - 12 marks
- c. State FOUR (4) Mechanical methods of family planning - 4 marks

Question Four

- a. List SIX (8) infection prevention measures practiced when inserting implants - 8 marks
- b. State the types and duration of effectiveness for implants - 4 marks
- c. Explain the physiology of lactational amenorrhea (LAM) - 5 marks
- d. Mention the THREE (3) conditions required for LAM - 3 marks

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – MAY 2012
HRGN 068 PUBLIC HEALTH NURSING
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ Hrs.
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

- a. State the three (3) important conditions that ensure the effectiveness of Lactation Amenorrhoea Method (LAM) as a natural family planning method. - 12 marks
- b. Explain four (4) advantages of LAM over other natural family planning methods - 8 marks

Question Two

Discuss the current policy on under 5 child feeding and nutritional needs in Ghana - 20 marks

Question Three

Write short notes on the following

- a. Routine Home Visits
- b. The role of the school nurse in the provision of school meals
- c. The relationship of the agent, Host and Environment in communicable diseases
- d. The steps to undertake during the outbreak of a communicable disease
- e. The responsibilities of mothers towards childhood immunization - 20 marks